

1

Supplementary Data

2

3 Figure S1. A) Mean parental species survival across year and habitat. B) Mean parental fruit number
 4 across habitats. Lines indicating relationships across habitats are not included for 2019 because sample
 5 sizes are insufficient. 2013 data is published in Ferris and Willis (2018) and re-analyzed here.

6

7 Figure S2. Proportion of individuals surviving in all sites based on planting date. The line indicates a
 8 summary line with a 95% confidence interval. A one-way ANOVA indicates that there is a significant
 9 difference in plant survival based on planting date ($F=77.2$, $p<.001$).

10

11

12 Figure S3. Proportion of total F4 hybrid individuals that flowered with presence of herbivory in 2013 and
13 2019. 2013 data is published in Ferris and Willis (2018) and re-analyzed here.

14

15

16 Figure S4. Trait correlation matrix for F₄ hybrid traits in 2019 in A.) Meadow and B.) Granite.

17

18

19

20 Figure S5. Correlation between seed and fruit is significant in meadows ($P < .001$, correlation coefficient =

21 0.309, $n = 1902$) and the granite outcrop ($P = 0.0036$, correlation coefficient = 0.172, $n = 838$).

Model	k	Log(L)	AIC	delta(i)	wi
Binomial					
Granite Fruit ~ FT X FW + L X PH	10	-81.038	183.4	0	0.999
Granite Seed ~ FT	8	-99.608	216.1	0	0.334
Meadow Fruit ~ FT X FW + L X PH	10	-145.679	312.1	0	0.195
Meadow Seed ~ FT X PH + FW	8	-162.887	342.3	0	0.431
Truncated Poisson					
Granite Fruit ~ L X PH + FW X FT	9	-224.734	467.5	0	0.445
Granite Seed ~ FT X O + PH X FW	9	-222.483	466.4	0	0.947
Meadow Fruit ~ L X PH + FT	7	-257.548	529.5	0	0.241
Meadow Seed ~ FT X PH + FW X L	9	-1012.73	2045.2	0	0.999

22

23 Table S1. Model selection for best fit linear and quadratic selection models of hybrid traits in 2019. For
24 each analysis, we report k, the number of parameters; Log(L), the likelihood score; AIC score, delta(i),
25 the difference between that model's AIC and the top model's AIC; and wi, the model weight. FT,
26 flowering time; FW, corolla width; L, leaf lobing; PH, height; O, for stigma-anther separation.

27

28

29

30

Year	Model	k	Log(L)	AIC	delta(i)	wi
2019	Survival Total ~ moisture*days*Habitat	11	272.649	-522.9	0	1
2013	Survival Total ~ moisture*days*habitat	11	488.0297	-954.06	0	0.499
Both	Survival Total ~ moisture*days+Habitat+year	9	318.120	-618.2	0	0.88
Both	Survival Meadow ~ moisture+days*Site+year	8	395.961	-775.8	0	0.958
Both	Survival Granite ~ moisture*days+Site+year	8	236.335	-456.6	0	1

31

32 Table S2. Model selection for best fit models of plant survival and environmental variables. For each
33 analysis, we report k, the number of parameters; Log(L), the likelihood score; AIC score, delta(i), the
34 difference between that model's AIC and the top model's AIC; and wi, the model weight.

35

36

37

38

39

40

41

42

43

Plant	Trait	Mean Granite	SE Granite	C _v Granite	Mean Meadow	SE Meadow	C _v Meadow
F ₄	FT	26.67****	0.033	0.193	41.21****	0.57	0.298
	Height	39.44	2.76	0.556	36.76***	0.84	0.487
	FW	8.2***	8.2	0.32	6.44***	6.42	0.403
	Leaf area	3158.74****	131.33	0.621	2560.26****	80.48	0.655
	Lobing	0.13****	0.004	0.446	0.14****	0.003	0.495
	O	-0.5	0.09	-	-0.56	0.07	-
<i>M. laciniatus</i>	FT	-	-		29.24***	2.41	0.34
	Height	-	-		41.82	4.58	0.452
	FW	-	-		3.2	28.38	0.65
	Leaf area	-	-		2701***	350.07	0.502
	Lobing	-	-		0.33	0.037	0.43
	O	-	-		-0.66	0.263	-
<i>M. guttatus</i>	FT	-	-		42.8***	2.64	0.333
	Height	-	-		36.27*	3.62	0.556
	FW	-	-		8.45	31.12	0.38
	Leaf area	-	-		2628.19***	365.07	0.708
	Lobing	-	-		0.09**	0.009	0.483
	O	-	-		-1.36	0.12	-

44

45 Table S3. Trait means, standard error, and coefficient of variance (C_v) from the 2019 experiment.

46 Significant variation in a trait mean is indicated by “*” within year and “*” across years, and significance

47 codes are as follows: P-value < 0.001***; 0.01**; 0.05*. FT, flowering time; FW, corolla width; O, for

48 stigma-anther separation.

49

50

51

Model	k	Log(L)	AIC	delta(i)	wi
Binomial					
Granite Fruit ~ FT X FW X PT + L X PH	14	-72.775	176.1	0	0.53
Granite Seed ~ FT	8	-99.608	216.1	0	0.334
Meadow Fruit ~ FT X FW + L X PH X PT	14	-138.765	307.0	0	0.417
Meadow Seed ~ FT X PH + FW	8	-162.887	342.3	0	0.431
Truncated Poisson					
Granite Fruit ~ L X PH X PT + FW X FT	13	-215.95	460.2	0	0.663
Granite Seed ~ FT X O + PH X FW	9	-222.483	466.4	0	0.947
Meadow Fruit ~ L X PH + FT + PT	8	-254.295	525.1	0	0.425
Meadow Seed ~ FT X PH + FW X L	9	-1012.73	2045.2	0	0.999

52

53 Table S4. Model selection for best fit linear and quadratic selection models of hybrid traits in 2019
54 including planting time. For each analysis, we report k, the number of parameters; Log(L), the likelihood
55 score; AIC score, delta(i), the difference between that model's AIC and the top model's AIC; and wi, the
56 model weight. FT, flowering time; FW, corolla width; L, leaf lobing; PH, height; O, stigma-anther
57 separation; PT, planting time.

58

59

60

61